

Utilization of Milkfish (*Chanos sp*) Bones for Reducing Lead (Pb) Contamination

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Abstract

Background: Good water quality is essential to meet all basic human needs. In Indonesia, water needs are met through both piped and non-piped sources, including shallow wells, groundwater, and existing springs. However, the presence of heavy metals in source water presents a significant challenge for water treatment. One effective water treatment technology is the use of biofilters, which can be made using discarded milkfish bones.

Methods: This study employs an experimental approach utilizing a biofilter reactor within a batch system, with a reactor volume of 1.5 liters. The experiment investigated contact times of 22 hours, 24 hours, and 26 hours, utilizing a combination of milkfish bone masses of 10 grams, 20 grams, and 30 grams, supplemented with the addition of 5 grams of zeolite. Lead (Pb) concentration was analyzed in the laboratory of PDAM Surya Sembada, Surabaya, Indonesia.

Results: The results indicated that the optimum removal efficiency of lead (Pb) was 66%, achieved with a contact time of 22 hours and a fish bone mass of 20 grams. Statistical analysis using a simple linear regression test revealed that contact time significantly influences the reduction of lead (Pb).

Conclusion: This study demonstrated that discarded milkfish bones can be effectively utilized as a biofilter to reduce the concentration of the heavy metal lead (Pb) in water. This research not only provides a solution for repurposing milkfish bone waste, which is typically not consumed, but also offers a sustainable method for mitigating heavy metal contamination in aquatic environments.

Keywords: biofilter; lead (Pb); milkfish bones

1. Introduction: Water is a fundamental necessity for all living organisms, particularly humans. Good water quality is essential to meet basic human needs such as drinking, cooking, and washing, as well as for various industrial production processes. Safe water is also the focus of the 6th Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) for 2030, which aims to ensure the availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all [1]. Specifically, Target 6.1 of the SDGs aims to "achieve universal and equitable access to safe and affordable drinking water for all by 2030." In Indonesia, according to data from the Directorate of Urban, Housing, and Settlements of the Ministry of National Development Planning/BAPPENAS, safe drinking water sources are defined as households using protected water sources. These include: (i) individual piped taps, (ii) shared piped taps, (iii) public taps or hydrants, (iv) water terminals, (v) water retailers, (vi) rainwater harvesting systems (PAH), (vii) protected springs, (viii) protected wells, and (ix) boreholes or pump wells [2]. However, in general, water needs in both urban and rural areas in Indonesia are met through a combination of piped and non-piped sources, including shallow wells, groundwater, and existing springs [3]. Additionally, piped systems are generally sourced from surface water, such as rivers and lakes.

On the other hand, many experts have demonstrated that clean water sources in Indonesia, both surface water and groundwater, have been polluted, as reported by Ishak et al. (2022), the concentration of several heavy metals, namely Fe, Mn, and Cu, in the Martapura River, South Kalimantan Province, has exceeded the threshold levels set by Government Regulation No. 22 of 2021 [4]. Another researcher noted that 13% of drinking water in Bandung, comprising 7.8% groundwater and 5.2% refill water, is considered unfit for consumption. This is due to concentrations of heavy metals such as As, Cd, Co, Hg, Mn, and Pb that exceed the maximum allowable limits, making the water unsuitable for consumption [5]. Contamination of water sources by heavy metals poses a major environmental and health concern because of the negative health impacts linked to the consumption of water containing heavy metals. Heavy metals can persist in soil and water for extended periods and move through the food chain, eventually accumulating in organisms. Many experts have investigated the dangers of heavy metals in humans. Philips & Fajemila (2024) reported a cancer risk in both children and adults from low to high levels of heavy metals, including Co, Pb, Mn, Ni, Cd, Cu, and Zn [6]. Other researchers have reported that heavy metals such as Zn, Cu, Pb, Cr, As, and Cd accumulate in fish and can potentially cause cancer in humans [7]. Given the significant health risks, it is essential to treat water before it can be safely used by humans.

Water treatment aims to purify highly polluted water to meet established quality standards. The treatment process typically varies based on the quality of the raw water. Common units involved in water treatment include coagulation-flocculation, sedimentation, filtration, and chlorination [8]. Filtration units operate using media that act as adsorbents, which can be either natural or synthetic. One effective natural adsorbent is derived from fish bones, specifically milkfish bones. In Indonesia, milkfish bones are readily available due to the high production rates in various fish processing facilities. The Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (KKP) reported that milkfish production in Indonesia reached 785,719 tons, valued at IDR 16.53 trillion, in 2022. This represents a slight increase of 0.12% from the previous year, which saw

production at 784,778 tons with a value of IDR 15.56 trillion [9]. The high production of milkfish correlates with a significant amount of milkfish bone waste. Utilizing milkfish bones as biofilters is highly beneficial for clean water treatment in Indonesia.

2. Methodology: This study employs an experimental approach utilizing a biofilter reactor within a batch system, with a reactor volume of 1.5 liters. The experiment investigated contact times of 22 hours, 24 hours, and 26 hours, utilizing a combination of milkfish bone masses of 10 grams, 20 grams, and 30 grams, supplemented with the addition of 5 grams of zeolite. In this study, zeolite was utilized both as a supplement and as a catalyst to facilitate the adsorption reaction for milkfish bone adsorption.

The preparation of milkfish bones into biofilters/adsorbents involves several stages:

1. Collection: Milkfish bones are collected from the central production and cultivation ponds in Kalanganyar Village, Sidoarjo, Indonesia.
2. Cleaning: The bones are cleaned using hot distilled water, then dried in the sun and in an oven at 120°C.
3. Carbon Preparation: The cleaned bones are placed in a furnace at 550°C until they become ash, then ground until smooth and sieved using a 100-mesh sieve.
4. Carbon Activation: The ash is immersed in 0.1 N NaOH and stirred with a magnetic stirrer at 350 rpm and 60°C for 2 hours.
5. Final Processing: The adsorbent is then filtered, placed in an oven at 80°C for 24 hours, and is ready for use.

The heavy metal of lead (Pb) waste used in this study was simulated using artificial lead waste in the form of $Pb(NO_3)_2$ at a concentration of 5,762 mg/L. Lead (Pb) concentration was analyzed in the laboratory of PDAM Surya Sembada, Surabaya, Indonesia.

3. Results: The research results on the final concentration of heavy metal (Pb) were obtained for contact times of 22 hours, 24 hours, and 26 hours. The results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: The final concentration of Pb

No	Reactors	Treatments	Contact Time	Initial Concentration of Pb (mg/L)	Final Concentration of Pb (mg/L).
1	R1	10 grams milkfish bone only	22	5,762	2,48
2	R2	10 grams milkfish bone + 5 grams zeolite	22	5,762	2,63
3	R3	20 grams milkfish bone + 5 grams zeolite	22	5,762	1,98
4	R4	30 grams milkfish bone + 5 grams zeolite	22	5,762	2,02
5	R5	10 grams milkfish bone only	24	5,762	3,23

6	R6	10 grams milkfish bone + 5 grams zeolite	24	5,762	4,36
7	R7	20 grams milkfish bone + 5 grams zeolite	24	5,762	4,05
8	R8	30 grams milkfish bone + 5 grams zeolite	24	5,762	4,88
9	R9	10 grams milkfish bone only	26	5,762	4,53
10	R10	10 grams milkfish bone + 5 grams zeolite	26	5,762	3,62
11	R11	20 grams milkfish bone + 5 grams zeolite	26	5,762	5,06
12	R12	30 grams milkfish bone + 5 grams zeolite	26	5,762	5,28

Based on the table, the highest reduction of Pb waste occurred in reactor 3, which used 20 grams of milkfish bones and 5 grams of zeolite with a contact time of 22 hours, resulting in a final Pb concentration of 1.98 mg/L. In contrast, the lowest reduction occurred in reactor 12, which used 30 grams of milkfish bones and 5 grams of zeolite with a contact time of 26 hours, resulting in a final Pb concentration of 5.2 mg/L.

The efficiency of each reactor is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The efficiency of Pb reduction in all treatments

As depicted in Figure 1, the highest Pb reduction efficiency of 65.64% was achieved in reactor 3, which used 20 grams of milkfish bones and 5 grams of zeolite with a contact time of 22 hours. In contrast, the lowest Pb reduction efficiency of 8.37% was observed in reactor 12, which used 30 grams of milkfish bones and 5 grams of zeolite with a contact time of 26 hours.

This research demonstrates the promising capability of milkfish bones in mitigating heavy metal contamination, specifically lead. When utilized independently, milkfish bones exhibit an efficiency of 56.96% within a 22-hour contact period. However, as the duration extends to 24 and 26 hours, their effectiveness diminishes to 21.38%. Thus, it is evident that the optimal concentration for milkfish bones alone stands at 10 grams. These findings emphasize the potential of milkfish bones as a natural remediation agent for heavy metal pollution.

Table 2 presents the statistical analysis of the effects of contact time and varying masses of milkfish bone adsorbent on the reduction of lead (Pb) concentration.

Table 2: Statistical analysis results

		Coefficients ^a					Collinearity	
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	-10.964	3.361		-3.263	.005		
	Contact time	.614	.140	.739	4.393	.000	1.000	1.000
2	(Constant)	3.231	.885		3.651	.002		
	Masses	.027	.041	.161	.653	.523	1.000	1.00

Statistical analysis of the effect of contact time on the reduction of Pb heavy metal concentration revealed a significant effect, with a significance value of $\alpha = 0.000$. The results indicate that the optimum contact time for maximum efficiency in reducing Pb metal concentration is 22 hours. On the other hand, the mass of fish bones did not significantly affect lead reduction, with a significance value of $\alpha = 0.523$. Nevertheless, the highest efficiency in reducing Pb concentration was achieved with a combination of 20 grams of milkfish bones and 5 grams of zeolite.

4. Discussion: Numerous studies have emphasized the efficacy of fish bones in mitigating heavy metal contamination, as exemplified by the work of Hernández-Cocoletzi *et.al* (2020), who developed adsorbents from fish bones to reduce Nickel levels. It is well-established that Hydroxyapatite (HAp), a biocrystalline compound composed of calcium, phosphorus, and hydrogen, with a chemical formula $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$, serves as an active adsorbent capable of sequestering these metal ions [10]. Researchers from Indonesia have found that Gurame fish bone powder is an effective adsorbent for Cu(II) metal, with an adsorption capacity of 7.2 mg/g and an adsorption efficiency of 89% [11]. However, the potential of milkfish bones as heavy metal adsorbents remains largely unexplored. The current study presents significant findings

on the use of milkfish bones as a biofilter to reduce Pb heavy metal.

It is assumed that the hydroxyapatite content in milkfish bones plays a crucial role in the Pb metal adsorption mechanism. Calcium hydroxyapatite can remove lead metal (Pb) through methods such as surface adsorption, cation substitution, and dissolution-precipitation. In the adsorption process, calcium hydroxyapatite acts on the surface, facilitating an ion exchange reaction between the surface and the lead (Pb) in the waste. The ion exchange reaction between lead metal and calcium hydroxyapatite is as follows:

The statistical analysis revealed that contact time significantly influenced the reduction of Pb levels. This indicates that varying the contact time of the adsorbent can yield different concentration in waste reduction. According to the findings of this study, the optimal contact time was 22 hours. Contact time refers to the duration needed for milkfish bones, acting as an adsorbent, to interact with the adsorbate, specifically Pb. The optimum contact time of 22 hours is necessary for the equilibrium of the adsorption reaction between milkfish bones and Pb waste. This result may vary depending on the type of adsorbent and adsorbate used. For instance, a study on the adsorption process using chitin extracted from shrimp shells to reduce phosphate levels determined that the optimal contact time for phosphate adsorption was 30 minutes [13]. Another study reported that adsorbents made from fish bones exhibited a maximum adsorption capacity for Methylene blue of 303.03 mg/g with a contact time of 180 minutes (3 hours) [14].

Conclusion: This study showed that discarded milkfish bones can be effectively used as a biofilter to lower lead (Pb) concentrations in water. Milkfish bones adsorbent exhibit an efficiency of 56.96% within a 22-hour contact period. This research provides a way to repurpose typically unused milkfish bone waste while offering a sustainable method to reduce heavy metal contamination in aquatic environments.

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